

EFFECT OF PRESSURE ON GOLD CYANIDE LEACHING

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ABSTRACT. Although the effect of high oxygen pressure on gold recoveries at elevated slurry temperatures was previously investigated, the sole effect of the pressure at ambient temperatures on cyanide leaching with the presence of nearly enough oxygen for the cyanide reactions to occur has not been found to be studied. This research work was carried out with the objective of investigating the effect of pressure on the recovery of gold from an oxide gold ore and flotation tailing (Carbon in leach (CIL) feed) samples during cyanide leaching process at room temperature. Pressure cyanidation experiments were run in a batch autoclave under different air and nitrogen gas pressures, and pH conditions. Atmospheric bottle roll leach tests for 24 and 8 hours resulted in 90.5% and 66.4% gold recoveries, respectively, whereas 8 hours batch autoclave leach tests under 90 psi air pressure resulted in 88.8% gold recovery from oxide ore samples. Flotation tailing samples leached under atmospheric and under 90 psi air pressure for 8 hours resulted in 16.8% and 34.5% gold recoveries, respectively.

Key words: cyanide, pressure leach, gold

Introduction

The process of cyanidation involves the dissolution of gold containing ores in dilute cyanide solution with the presence of base and oxygen (Park, 1897).

During dissolution of gold in cyanide solution, as a first step, oxygen is reduced, and hydrogen peroxide is formed as an intermediate product and hydrogen peroxide becomes the oxidising agent in the second step. The overall chemical reactions are presented below (Senanayake, 2005).

The summation of equations (1) and (2) is presented in the following equation (Elsner, 1846).

In heterogeneous systems, cyanide ions and dissolved oxygen in the slurries will diffuse through the pores of the particles as follows according to the Fick's Law (Habashi, 1967):

$$\frac{d(O_2)}{dt} = \frac{D_{O_2}}{\delta} A_1 \{ [O_2] - [O_2]_i \} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d(CN^-)}{dt} = \frac{D_{CN^-}}{\delta} A_2 \{ [CN^-] - [CN^-]_i \} \quad (5)$$

where $\frac{d(O_2)}{dt}$, $\frac{d(CN^-)}{dt}$ - O_2 and CN^- dissolution rate (moles/sec), D_{O_2} , D_{CN^-} - diffusion coefficients of dissolved oxygen and cyanide (cm^2/sec), $[O_2]$, $[CN^-]$ - O_2 and CN^- concentration in the solution (moles/ml), $[O_2]_i$, $[CN^-]_i$ - O_2 and CN^- concentration at the interference (moles/ml), A_1 , A_2 - surface area where leaching reactions occur (cm^2), δ - boundary layer thickness, cm.

Gold is leached within the micropores of the solids where the rate of lixiviant diffusion will be directly affected by its pressure gradient in addition to the boundary layer conditions on the solid surfaces.

Relationship between the pressure gradient and a liquid' flow rate into a macroscopic channel that is causing wetting of the pores is shown by the Poiseuille flow as follows (Mott, 2015):

$$\bar{v} = \frac{D^2}{32 \mu} \delta p \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{v}$ - flowrate average, D - channel diameter, μ - liquid viscosity, δp - pressure gradient.

For the microscopic channel case the capillary effect should also be taken into account for the balance between the applied pressure and the effects of surface tension. This equilibrium is described by the Laplace-Young equation (Ibach, 2006):

$$p_{in} = \frac{4\Delta\gamma}{D} \quad (7)$$

where p_{in} - infiltration pressure, $\Delta\gamma$ - excess solid-liquid interfacial tension, D - channel diameter.

As shown on the equations 6 and 7, by the application of the external pressure, lixiviant can be forced into the pores of solid particles which indicates that fluid motion rate on a solid surface is governed by the pressure.

Based on this hypothesis, the research work carried out with the objective of investigating the effect of pressure on the recovery of gold during cyanide leaching process at room temperature.

The testing focused on leaching of ore samples in the presence of pressurised air and nitrogen, while having atmospheric pressure air within vapour space of the batch autoclave at the beginning of each experiment.

All sample preparations and assaying throughout the experimental study were performed utilising industry accepted standards.

Leaching experiments were applied to grab samples of an oxide ore and flotation tailings in order to compare pressure leaching effects on samples of different mineralogical compositions. Pressure leach experiments were run in a two-litre batch autoclave under different air/nitrogen gas pressures and pH conditions.

Experimental

Samples

Experiments were conducted on two different samples, an oxide gold ore and flotation tailings (CIL Feed). Leco analysis for total sulphur, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), cyanide shake tests with atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) and fire assaying were conducted on pulverised dry head and leached samples of the oxide ore and flotation tailings.

The oxide ore's average total gold (AuFA) and cyanide soluble gold (AuCN) contents were 0.222 and 0.213 troy ounce per ton, respectively whereas flotation tailings samples AuFA and AuCN amounts were 0.028 and 0.0124 troy ounce per ton, respectively. Fire assay analyses showed that oxide ore has nearly eight times more gold content than the flotation tailings. The cyanide shake tests showed that 44% of the total gold amount was amenable to cyanide leaching for flotation tailing samples whereas cyanide leachable gold content for the oxide ore samples was 96% of the total gold content. The sulphide sulphur content of the oxide ore and flotation tailings were found as 0.159% and 0.337%, respectively. Test samples are shown on Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Golden Days ore sample

Fig.2. Flotation tailings sample

Table 1 and Table 2 show the oxide ore and flotation tailings samples' elemental analyses. CTOT, CAI, AuPR, SRO, STO are total carbon, organic carbon, preg rob material, sulphate sulphur and total sulphur respectively. Both oxide ore and flotation tailings samples were primarily selected for this experimental test work because of their low sulphide sulphur content. The first set of experiments were planned to be conducted on oxide ore samples with high grade gold content and the second set of experiments with lower gold grade flotation tailing samples.

The high gold content of oxide ore samples provided better observation of recovery changes during the experiments. A second set of experiments were conducted with flotation tailings samples in order to investigate the effect of pressure cyanidation on the recoveries where cyanide soluble gold was relatively lower than the oxide samples.

Experimental Procedures

Flotation tailings samples had particle size of $P_{80} = 200$ mesh. In order to reduce the size of the oxide ore grab samples, a three-stage crushing-screening and a grinding procedure was applied. Crushed oxide ore product was weighed and fed to the ball mill to reduce its particle size distribution to flotation tailings samples' size distribution. Following the grinding, the mill product was collected and left to dry in an oven at 35 °C for 24 hours. The dried grind product was used as feed for leaching experiments.

Cyanide leaching experiments were conducted at 25 °C and under 12.4 psi atmospheric pressure, and 30, 60, 90 psi autoclave pressures for 8 hours. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the experimental setups. Oxide ore were also leached for 24-hour period under atmospheric pressure by bottle roll equipment with the addition of same amount of CaO as in the 8-hour period experiments.

Table 1. Oxide ore samples

Type	Weight	Sample name	Type	Ag (ppm)	Al (ppm)	As (ppm)
Head	300 g +	Golden Days oxide ore - head assay	Au/Ag ore	3.314	576.658	61.97
AUCN (OPT)	AUFA1 (OPT)	AUFA2 (OPT)	AUPR (OPT)	Ba (ppm)	Be (ppm)	Bi (ppm)
0.2126	0.2217	0.2223	0.0098	18.729	0	0.669
CAI (%)	Ca (ppm)	Cd (ppm)	Co (ppm)	Cr (ppm)	CTOT (%)	Cu (ppm)
0.08	264.081	0.581	5.263	224.263	0.048	67.2
Fe (ppm)	Hg (ppm)	Li (ppm)	Mg (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Mo (ppm)	Na (ppm)
14755.7	0.133	0.003	434.366	134.883	6.197	219.708
Ni (ppm)	Pb (ppm)	P (ppm)	Sb (ppm)	Se (ppm)	Sn (ppm)	Sr (ppm)
41.774	6.098	64.337	6.059	0	0.023	1.553
SRO (%)	STOI (%)	Te (ppm)	Tl (ppm)	Tl (ppm)	V (ppm)	Zn (ppm)
0.051	0.21	14.047	27.892	0	10.645	13.108

Table 2. Flotation tailings samples

Type	Weight	Sample name	Type	Ag (ppm)	Al (ppm)	As (ppm)
Leach tails	+100 g	Flotation tailings head assay	Au ore	0	3452.55	976.179
AUCN (OPT)	AUFA1 (OPT)	AUFA2 (OPT)	AUPR (OPT)	Ba (ppm)	Be (ppm)	Bi (ppm)
0.0124	0.0288	0.0271	0	3440.11	0.243	3.092
CAI (%)	Ca (ppm)	Cd (ppm)	Co (ppm)	Cr (ppm)	CTOT (%)	Cu (ppm)
0.045	2969.37	2.496	6.384	16.219	0.098	64.243
Fe (ppm)	Hg (ppm)	Li (ppm)	Mg (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Mo (ppm)	Na (ppm)
12237	4.059	2.142	659.193	45.816	22.687	352.847
Ni (ppm)	Pb (ppm)	P (ppm)	Sb (ppm)	Se (ppm)	Sn (ppm)	Sr (ppm)
43.713	72.598	684.768	45.343	2.572	0.039	116.836
SRO (%)	STOI (%)	Te (ppm)	Tl (ppm)	Tl (ppm)	V (ppm)	Zn (ppm)
0.487	0.824	0	25.354	6.441	140.249	375.235

During the autoclave leaching experiments, the vessel was pressurised by pure nitrogen gas or air. All leaching experiments were conducted with addition of a base or under natural pH conditions of the samples without addition of a base. Table 3 summarises pressure cyanidation experimental conditions for both ore types at 8-hour leaching period.

Table 3. Autoclave experiments summary

Pressure (psi)	Air pressure		Nitrogen pressure	
	Base addition		Base addition	
90	None	CaO	None	CaO
60				
30				

None of the pressurising gases were purged through the pulp inside the autoclave. Pressurising gases were injected to the autoclave through the pressure inlet valve on top of the autoclave head and the gases accumulated above the slurry inside the autoclave.

Nitrogen gas was used as a pressurising agent to minimise effect of increased dissolved oxygen amount in the solution and to be able to observe the pressure effect on gold leaching. However, at the beginning of each experiment, 1350 cm³ of air was present in the empty top portion of the autoclave under atmospheric conditions. The air left in the autoclave was not purged by nitrogen gas out of the autoclave to ensure the presence of enough oxygen for the cyanide leaching reactions to occur.

First set of bottle roll experiments were conducted with NH₄OH, NaOH and CaO as pH modifier for leach kinetics comparison purposes. Calcium oxide (CaO) was used as pH modifier for rest of the cyanidation experiments since it is the most common pH modifier of cyanide leaching process in the mining industry. The oxide ore and flotation tailing samples had natural slurry pH values around 8.3 and 6.8, respectively. Due to lower natural pH value of the flotation tailings slurries, higher lime amounts were added to the solutions in order have similar pH conditions with the oxide ore pressure leaching experiments.

Fig. 3. Bottle roll set-up

Fig. 4. Autoclave

The amount of calcium oxide added during the flotation tailings pressure leaching experiments was 0.55 grams per 400

grams of dry sample feed (2.75 pound per dry short ton of floatation tailings) whereas this amount was 0.2 g CaO for 400 g of dry sample feed (1 pound per dry short ton of ore) for the Golden Days oxide ore.

All experiments regardless of sample type were conducted with addition of 0.4 grams of sodium cyanide (NaCN) for 400 g of dry sample (2 pounds for dry short ton of ore). Silver nitrate with p-dimethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine indicator titration was used to measure free cyanide in leach solutions at the end of the tests.

Results and discussion

Grinding experiments

After completing oxide ore crushing with two different size, 5" x 7", 2.25" x 3", jaw crushers and a roll crusher with -10 mesh reduction size, a grinding study was conducted for Golden Days ore samples. Grinding experiments were conducted in order to determine grinding time required to obtain floatation tailings particle size distribution, 80% passing 200 mesh. Total of four grinding experiments were conducted. Experiment results are provided on Figure 5.

It was concluded that Golden Days ore samples were to be ground for 48 minutes in order to have floatation tailings samples' particle size, 80% of the particles passing 200 mesh.

Fig. 5. Golden Days samples – grind study results

Bottle roll experiments

Bottle roll experiments were conducted to determine cyanide leachability of the samples by the industry accepted standard technique. Initial bottle roll and autoclave experiments were conducted for different mixing rates to determine a mixing rate both for autoclave and bottle rolls that would give similar recovery values for the same leaching time at atmospheric pressure.

As shown on the Table 4, bottle roll tests resulted in recoveries of more than 87% gold recoveries at the end of 24 hours under atmospheric conditions.

Table 5 shows the resulting gold recoveries after 8 h leach time for different bottle mixing rates. Leach kinetics of bottle roll experiments at different rolling rates are presented on Figure 6. The bottle roll experiments where ammonium hydroxide was used as pH modifier gave slightly higher gold recoveries compared to the experiments where calcium oxide (CaO) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were used for 24 hour leaching period at the bottle mixing rates of 81 and 110 rpm. Cyanide leaching kinetics curves for the experiments where NaOH was used as a base resulted in higher leaching rates compared to experiments conducted with CaO addition.

Table 4. Golden Days samples 24 h bottle roll gold recoveries under atmospheric pressure of 12.4 psi

Exp. #	Base type	pH	Mixing rate (rpm)	AuFA Rec. (%)
8BR	CaO	11.7	110	90.5
6BR	CaO	11.6	98	89.1
1BR	CaO	11.5	81	87.4
9BR	NaOH	10.9	110	91.3
2BR	NaOH	11.1	98	89.0
5BR	NaOH	11.1	81	88.6
3BR	NH ₄ OH	10.7	110	93.3
10BR	NH ₄ OH	10.6	81	89.8

Table 5. Golden Days samples 8 h bottle roll gold recoveries under atmospheric pressure of 12.4 psi

Exp. No	Base	% AuFA Recovery	Bottle Roll (rpm)
8BR	CaO	71.0	110
6BR	CaO	67.6	98
1BR	CaO	66.4	81
9BR	NaOH	70.8	110
2BR	NaOH	69.3	98
5BR	NaOH	67.0	81
3BR	NH ₄ OH	71.7	110
10BR	NH ₄ OH	66.5	81

Between 65% to 72% of the total gold (AuFA) contained in Golden Days ore was leached at the end of the 8 h cyanide bottle roll experiments. Bottle roll tests showed that at the end of the 24-hour period 87% of the total gold was recovered by adding CaO as a base and rolling the bottles at 81 rpm. As expected, higher mixing rates resulted in higher gold dissolution rates by reducing diffusion layer thickness and increasing mass transfer rates of oxygen and cyanide during leaching.

As it can be observed from from Figure 6 bottle roll leaching experiments where CaO was used as a base has shown slower gold dissolution kinetics and lower recoveries at the end of the 24 hours leaching period. This can be explained by the retarding effect of the lime on gold dissolution. Formation of calcium peroxide film on the surface of the gold particles occurs when lime reacts with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in the slurry solution by the following reaction (Barsky, 1934)

Autoclave experiments

Golden Days samples (Oxide ore)

Autoclave experiments were conducted to investigate room temperature pressure cyanidation effects on gold recoveries. Initial autoclave experiments were conducted at 200, 350 and 400 rpm impeller rotational speeds to find the right mixing rates that would give similar recovery values with the bottle roll experiments.

Fig. 6. Golden Days bottle roll test results – recoveries versus time

Two hundred (200) rpm rate was not enough to suspend the particles and caused settling of the solid particles to the bottom of the autoclave vessel. The minimum impeller rotational speed was found to be 300 rpm in order to have all solid particles suspending in solutions. Mixing rates for bottle roll and autoclave experiments for the same recoveries were found to be 81 rpm and 400 rpm respectively. Bottle roll experiment #1 had 66.4% of the total recovered after 8 hours of leaching. The gold recoveries increased with the increased pressure levels. The resulting gold recoveries from both bottle roll and autoclave experiments and percent gold recovery increases for the pressure cyanidation experiments are presented on Table 6. The comparison of the recoveries between the bottle roll and autoclave experiments for different pressure levels are presented in Figure 7.

It was expected that increased gold recoveries would result in higher cyanide consumption. But examining all pressure leaching experiments that resulted in higher recoveries, the cyanide usage of these experiments showed lower cyanide consumptions compared to bottle roll experiments.

Golden Days ore has natural pH values of 8.3. During gold dissolution by cyanide (Equation 3), the leach solution becomes more basic due to formation of hydroxide ions (OH⁻). As a result of this, the pH of the solution for the experiments conducted with Golden Days samples under air pressure without addition of base rose to 10.1 which is very close to the optimum pH value (10.3) for gold cyanide leaching.

The experiments at natural pH values of oxide ore samples which were close to the optimum leaching pH value showed higher gold recoveries compared to the ones conducted with base addition resulting in higher pH and lower NaCN consumption. However, the pH – cyanide consumption – gold recovery relationship observed for the experiments conducted under nitrogen pressure with addition of CaO (Experiment sets 17, 18, 19) and without addition of CaO (Experiment sets 38, 39, 40) were opposite to the ones conducted under air pressure.

The experiments conducted under nitrogen pressure and without any base resulted in higher cyanide consumptions and reduced gold recoveries compared to the experiments conducted with base addition as shown on Table 6.

Prior to pressurising the autoclave, air was present within the empty portion of the autoclave (1350 ml at 12.4 psi) since the air was not flushed out prior to experiments. Following the pressurisation of the autoclave, the dissolved oxygen amount in the slurry would be expected to increase. But the dissolved oxygen amount in the slurry was lower when the reactor was pressurised with pure nitrogen gas compared to when the air was the pressurising agent since the contained oxygen in the pressurised air would cause more oxygen dissolution into the slurry. The higher cyanide consumption and lower gold recoveries observed with no base addition and nitrogen gas pressurisation experiments may be due to the non-optimal [CN⁻/O₂] ratio and pH variations in the slurry causing lower gold dissolution rates and enhancing the decomposition of cyanide due to reactions with other metals, i.e. iron, present in the ore.

Leaching kinetics

Golden Days samples leaching kinetic curves of the bottle roll and autoclave experiments are presented on the next four figures. Figure 8 shows the dissolution kinetics of experiments where lime (CaO) was added to the solution and air used as a pressurising agent, whereas Figure 9 shows the gold dissolution kinetics when the nitrogen gas was used as a pressurising agent. The case where applied gas was air without the addition of base into the leach solution is presented on Figure 10.

The leach kinetic curves presented below also point out a higher kinetic rate with the increase in pressure levels. Also all four curves presented show that the gold recovery growths with increased pressure levels are independent from the solution pH values since the pressure effect on gold recoveries mainly resulted from a physical effect (increased lixiviant diffusion rate into the micropores of the solids), not from a chemical effect on the gold dissolution rates.

Flotation tailings

Additional experiments with flotation tailings (CIL feed) samples were conducted to compare the pressure effect on recoveries for the samples with different mineralogical composition. The main difference in the results between Golden Days samples and flotation tailings were the overall sample cyanide soluble gold (AuCN) and total gold (AuFA) values.

Table 6. Golden Days – AuFA recoveries for 8 h leaching time

Exp. No	Press. (psi)	Press. Gas type	Base	NaCN Cons. (lb/st of ore)	Final pH	AuFA Rec. (%)	Δ AuFA Rec. (%)
1	12.4	-	CaO	2.32	11.5	66.4	-
14	90	Air	CaO	2.14	11.5	88.8	33.7
15	60	Air	CaO	2.25	11.4	87.7	32.1
16	30	Air	CaO	2.28	11.9	82.4	24.1
18	90	N ₂	CaO	1.30	11.0	90.6	36.5
17	60	N ₂	CaO	0.98	11.1	87.6	31.9
19	30	N ₂	CaO	1.32	11.3	85.9	29.4
35	90	Air	-	1.79	10.1	93.1	40.2
36	60	Air	-	1.55	9.8	87.9	32.4
37	30	Air	-	1.21	10.1	85.6	28.9
38	90	N ₂	-	1.92	10.0	90.0	35.5
39	60	N ₂	-	2.18	10.2	86.0	29.5
40	30	N ₂	-	2.01	10.1	83.0	25.0

Fig. 7. Bottle roll (BRT) and pressure leaching recoveries – Golden Days samples 8 h leach

Fig. 10. Leaching kinetic curves – experiments 1, 35, 36, 37 – Golden Days samples 8 h leach

Fig. 8. Leaching kinetic curves – experiments 1, 14, 15, 16 – Golden Days samples 8 h leach

Fig. 9. Leaching kinetic curves – experiments 1, 17, 18, 19 – Golden Days samples 8 h leach

Experimental results are presented with and without base addition for the leaching of the flotation tails at atmospheric and elevated pressures. The flotation tailing samples had lower natural pH values (around 6.8) compared with Golden Days ore samples. Due to lower natural pH value of the flotation tailings samples, higher lime amounts were added to the solution in order to have similar pH conditions with the Golden Days pressure leaching experiments.

The pressure leaching experiments conducted by adding lime to the leach slurry showed higher gold recoveries than experiments with no base addition due to the increase from the natural pH of the flotation tailings slurry to close to optimum cyanide leaching pH values (10.3).

Pressure cyanidation experiments conducted at pH values less than 10 caused a decrease in gold recoveries and an increase in cyanide consumption compared to experiments conducted with average pH values between 10.6 and 11.0. This could be explained by the effect of the pH values on formation of cyanide species and reactions with other metals consuming cyanide.

On the other hand, most pressure cyanidation experiments at any pH value resulted in higher gold recoveries compared to experiments conducted at atmospheric pressures. As presented on Table 7, gold recoveries increased up to 105% for the same time of leaching at elevated pressure levels (90 psi) compared to the experiments conducted at atmospheric conditions.

Table 7. Flotation Tailings – AuFA Recoveries for 8 h leaching time

Exp. No	Press. (psi)	Gas type	Base	NaCN Cons. (lb/st of ore)	Final pH	AuFA Rec. (%)	Δ AuFA Rec. (%)
28	12.4	-	CaO	1.76	10.9	16.8	-
29	90	Air	CaO	1.68	10.6	34.5	105.4
30	60	Air	CaO	1.36	10.7	29.0	72.6
44	30	Air	CaO	1.25	10.6	23.0	36.9
25	90	N ₂	CaO	1.30	10.7	29.7	76.8
26	60	N ₂	CaO	1.58	10.6	25.2	50.0
43	30	N ₂	CaO	1.57	11.0	18.8	11.9
32	90	Air	-	2.21	8.1	26.8	59.5
33	60	Air	-	2.23	8.1	25.9	54.2
34	30	Air	-	2.33	8.0	21.3	26.8
22	90	N ₂	-	2.27	7.7	22.0	30.9
23	60	N ₂	-	2.17	8.4	17.0	1.2
24	30	N ₂	-	2.18	7.9	16.0	-

Pressure cyanidation experiments conducted with air pressure resulted in higher total gold (AuFA) recoveries compared to the experiments where nitrogen gas was used for pressurising the autoclave.

Experiment 24 (No base, 30 psi N₂ pressure) and 23 (No base, 60 psi, N₂ pressure) gave similar total gold (AuFA) recoveries when compared to the experiment that was run under atmospheric conditions. This could be caused by combination of low pH and low dissolved oxygen amount in the solution causing lower reaction rates for gold dissolution.

Leaching Kinetics

Figure 11 presents the recoveries on the flotation tailings samples for each pressure level. The leaching kinetic curves of the reactions for different pH and pressure levels are shown on Figures 12 - 14. Kinetic curves for pressure cyanidation of flotation tails also show the same relationship between recoveries and pressure levels as in the oxide ore experimental work, except the experiments when no base was added. Leaching of ore particles is a diffusion-controlled reaction. It was hypothesised that higher pressure levels cause an increase in the lixiviant diffusion in and out of the micropores of the solids. As a result, reaction rates and gold recoveries were higher for the pressure cyanide leaching experiments than the atmospheric leaching conditions at the same time of leaching at room temperature.

Fig. 11. Pressure effect on gold recoveries – flotation tailings samples 8 h leach

Fig. 12. Leaching kinetic curves – experiments 28, 25, 26, 43 – flotation tailings samples 8 h leach

Another effect of the increased pressure was the increase in oxygen partial pressures which causes higher dissolved oxygen concentrations in leach solution. Increase in the dissolved oxygen concentration can improve the reaction rates as long as the free cyanide ions are not the limiting factor and the solid particles are suspending in solution with the sufficient amount of leachable metal.

Explaining the recovery increase by the increase in dissolved oxygen amount is a valid argument if applied pressurising gas contains oxygen, which in this case is air. For this reason, to investigate the pure effect of pressure on leachant diffusivity into the solid particle micropores experiments were conducted with a minimal amount of oxygen present for the reactions to complete.

An inert gas, pure nitrogen, was added as a pressurising agent for a set of autoclave tests for oxide and flotation tailings samples. The experiments conducted with the nitrogen gas pressure also resulted in higher gold recoveries compared to atmospheric leaching experiments for the same leaching time and proved the pressure effect on the diffusivity during cyanide leaching.

Fig. 13. Leaching kinetic curves – experiments 28, 32, 33, 34 – flotation tailings samples 8 h leach

Fig. 14. Leaching kinetic curves – experiments 28, 25, 29 – flotation tailings samples 8 h leach

Conclusion

The pressure cyanidation experiments were conducted with the primary aim of investigating the pressure effect on the gold dissolution rate for the cyanide soluble gold. The findings of this study are summarised as follows:

- The rate of gold dissolution increases with the increased pressure levels inside the reactor at ambient temperatures.
- Test work showed that cyanide soluble gold was able to be recovered faster under pressure leaching conditions. 8-hour autoclave leaching under 90 psi pressure recovered nearly as much as gold by 24-hour bottle roll leach under atmospheric conditions.
- The oxygen content of the pressurising gas has effect on gold dissolution rates due to partial pressure of the oxygen gas.
- Effect of pressure on recoveries cyanide leaching experiments was observed on cyanide soluble gold amounts for both type of the samples.
- Leach pressure levels and cyanide consumption rates did not have a direct relationship.
- Cyanide consumption rates of pressure cyanidation test work conducted with a base addition was lower compared to the bottle roll test (Exp#1). On the other hand, cyanide consumption was higher for the experiments where a base was not added to the pressure leaching process compared to the bottle roll test (Exp#1).
- The pH level influences gold dissolution rate and the optimum pH level for the gold dissolution were observed between pH values 10.0 and 10.5.
- Higher slurry mixing rates up to a level during cyanidation improve the rate of gold leaching.

- Bottle roll leach experiments where lime (CaO) was used as base resulted in lower gold dissolution kinetics compared to the sodium hydroxide (NaOH) due to the retarding effect of lime.

Future work

This research has only been undertaken in a batch autoclave. Additional test work in a closed-circuit pilot plant is recommended to determine the impact of a closed-circuit pressurised continuous system on gold recovery values, retention times and industrial applicability of the process.

Additionally, further research on pressure leaching with alternative lixiviants such as thiosulfate, thiocyanate, thiourea in both base and acidic solutions should be investigated to determine economic competitiveness of these reagents to cyanide, using this high-pressure process.

The effect of pressure leaching at room temperature should also be investigated on different metallic ores beneficiation processes such as sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) leaching of copper ores. These experiments can be further applied to non-conventional methods such as bio-oxidation to investigate various potential process improvements.

Pressure cyanidation leaching experimental work can be further expanded to optimise parameters such as the pulp density, pH, pressure level, leach time, cyanide consumption and dissolved oxygen. At the end of the test work an industry applicable flowsheet can be generated to use this technology.

At very low pH values, HCN gas will be formed during cyanidation process. Since vapour pressure of HCN gas is 100 kPa (14.5 psi) at room temperature (Smith, Mudder, 1991), there is a possibility of the HCN bubbles to be reduced in leach solution and at elevated pressures where HCN will not volatilise and thus will stay in solution inside the reactor. Additional pure gold pressure leaching experiments with acidic solution conditions should be conducted to investigate gold dissolution rates by dissolved HCN, its effects on reagent consumptions and on the activity coefficient of the reagent ions.

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